
Performance Appraisal for Professional Development

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DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.15559730

Abstract:

Professional development is not something that can be forced, but teachers need to understand the need to take responsibility for their own professional development and to keep up to date with research and development in the subject they teach in this paper author has described performance appraisal for professional development.

Introduction:

In this century the need of hour is to faster teaching excellence in education and create a new cadre of well qualified and competent teachers who understand the global dimensions of their subjects as the student population become more diverse and demanding teachers need to become better at helping their student. In any given teaching learning situation the teachers is considered to be the main factor first teacher has to be motivated in order to motivate his student. The quality of an educational system depends to a great extent on well educated well equipped and well contented teacher.

Teacher has to develop personally and professionally in order to become an effective teacher. Professional development is not something that can be forced but teachers need to understand the need to take responsibility for their own professional development and to keep upto date with research and development in the subject they teach.

Professional development serves a number of purposes.

- To improve the job performance skill of an individual teacher.
- To extend the experience of an individual teacher for carrier development or promotion purpose
- To enhance the general education of an individual
- To promote job satisfaction.
- To enable teacher to visualize and prepare for the change.
- To improve student's learning.

Today some of the teacher are not in tune with the changing need of education, some of them lack motivation and initiative to raise their level of performance to meet the changing need. In recent years efforts have been made to use appraisals for motivation for effective communication for better relationship for goal setting and for inspiring total performance of the institution as well as individuals.

A consistent performance appraisal system supports teacher in their professional

development and promotes effective teaching to enhance student learning and achievement.

Purpose of Appraisal:

There are number of purpose of performance appraisal including reviewing performance assessing training need and making future plans. The goal and purpose of performance appraisal may be summarized in two categories: evaluative and developmental.

The main aim of the evaluation is to identify the gap. This gap occurs when performance does not meet the standards set by the institution as acceptable and the development purpose include research, feedback, career development human resources planning performance improvement and communication. An effective developmental tool is required to highlight areas for improvement, strength to build on, and identification of training needs. One of the purpose of the performance appraisal system is to promote professional growth.

‘Craft’ Identifies:

Many dimension in the relationship between teachers performance appraisal and their professional development as follows.

1. Appraisal provides opportunities for reflection, introspection and for feedback from others.
2. Appraisal is a way of identifying professional development need.
3. Appraisal can be used to evaluate the effectiveness of professional development at the review meetings.

4. Appraisal suggests areas for professional development on regular basis.

Why Appraise Performance?

One of the main duties of the principal is to appraise the teachers and identify their training need and then conduct the necessary training programmes through the means of workshop, seminars or other in service training programmes. It is important to examine whether proper appraisal is undertaken and the obtained result is used to design the professional development programme for teachers.

An established performance appraisal system identified the successes and weakness of the teachers and provides accurate information on their current performance. The process of performance appraisal provides a way of moving from identifying needs for the professional development to setting up a series of action.

Cyril and Poster:

Claim that the well prepared appraisal system will benefit both the individual staff and the institution they identified the benefits performance appraisal as:

1. Enhancing self-esteem and self-confidence.
2. Providing the opportunity to initiative problem solving and counseling interview.
3. Providing the means where by the individual can influence the organization.
4. Facilitating the identification of talent.

5. Integrating the individual and the organization.
6. Encouraging self-development and personal initiative

Conclusion:

Appraisal which has been designed and implemented with the main purpose of professional development, so that it can only have a positive result for teacher performance appraisal system has an important role to play in any institution.

The success of an institution of country depends on the quality of the people human resourced is the most valuable asset of any institution it is more valuable than capital or equipment people can be our biggest asset or our biggest liability hence performance appraisal system must be used as an important tool for the development of teachers and for quality education.

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